

Against Epistocracy¹

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Abstract

The paper discusses Jason Brennan's arguments in support of epistocracy, the idea that political decisions should be made by experts rather than by non-expert voters. Brennan's central argument is epistemological. He argues that voters are hopelessly ignorant when it comes to political issues and that this is a good reason not to let them exercise political power over others—the consequences of them doing so are quite simply too negative. I argue that while it is correct that good decisions need be made on the basis of knowledge, we should not underestimate the epistemic strengths of representative democracies. Moreover, I argue, political decisions depend not only on factual beliefs but on values, on what our goals are, and there are very strong reasons not to hand over the goals of society to unelected experts who cannot be held democratically accountable. The idea of epistocracy is an interesting philosophical thought experiment, illuminating the importance of knowledge in a well-functioning political system, but we are well advised not to experiment with it in the real world.

Keywords: democracy, epistocracy, experts, rationality, knowledge, values

Introduction

Since around 2016, the world has experienced a populist wave, with an increasing number of politicians and parties representing a form of right-wing nationalist populism coming into power. Political scientists characterize populism as a “thin ideology,” with little substantive content in terms of policies, which explains why there are versions of populism on both the right and the left.² Instead, three core ideas are identified: anti-pluralism, a pronounced anti-elitism and the idea that there is a fundamental antagonism between the (real) people and a morally corrupt elite. Translated into contemporary politics, the anti-elitism and antagonism have been expressed as a campaign against the role of experts in democracy. During the EU referendum, when the experts counselled against the United Kingdom leaving the European Union, the British politician Michael Gove famously declared that “people have had enough of experts.” Similar anti-expert sentiments have been a central theme in the politics of Donald Trump

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² See, for instance, Weale (2018).

since he first entered the political scene in 2015 and characterizes populist parties throughout Europe.³

The polar opposite of populism is arguably epistocracy—a system where political decisions are made by the knowledgeable. People defending such a system argue that societal decisions are too complex, and too important, to be left to people who lack the required knowledge. Hence, they argue, democracy is a fundamentally flawed system. In this paper, I shall discuss the central arguments in defense of epistocracy, in particular as formulated by the philosopher Jason Brennan. I shall argue that while it is correct that good decisions need be made on the basis of knowledge, we should not underestimate the epistemic strengths of representative democracies. Moreover, I argue, political decisions depend not only on factual beliefs but on values, on what our goals are, and there are very strong reasons not to hand over the goals of society to unelected experts who cannot be held democratically accountable. A well-functioning political system needs to avoid both of the extremes—the populist rejection of knowledge-based decisions as well as the epistocratic assumption that all of political decision making should be made by experts.

The Rationality of Voting⁴

In March 2017, the world-famous evolutionary biologist Richard Dawkins wrote an outraged article about the EU referendum that had taken place in June 2016. He complained that he had never asked to have a vote on an issue as complex as that of EU membership. He wrote that he immediately realized that leaving the EU would be infinitely complex, and that as far as he could tell, the Remain side was the one that made use of rational, evidence-based arguments, while the Leave side's arguments tended towards being emotional and, not infrequently, xenophobic. He thus voted for the UK to remain in the EU, but he would have preferred not to vote at all since he simply lacked the competence to answer the question in the first place. In the article, he opposes the Leave campaign's criticism of experts and its claim that the real expert was the British voter and writes that "you might as well call a nationwide plebiscite to decide whether Einstein got his algebra right or let passengers vote on which runway the pilot should land on" (Dawkins, 2017). Dawkins admits that this makes him an

³ The anti-expert sentiment is also translated into an anti-science attitude, with populists across Europe driving a form of general science skepticism (See Rekker, 2021, 2023). Underlying the rejection of expertise, is a fundamental skepticism of representative democracy distinctive of all forms of populism. It is held that a "true" democracy should be a more immediate expression of the will of the people, where the mediating role of expert knowledge as a basis for political decisions is rejected.

⁴ There is another debate concerning the rationality of voting that I will not address here, relating to the question of whether it is rational to vote at all, given the fact that one single vote will not make any difference. See Brennan (2020).

elitist but wonders what is wrong with that. We want elite surgeons who know their anatomy, he argues, elite pilots who know how to fly a plane, elite engineers who build safe bridges, and elite teachers who know how to educate the next generation and give them the opportunity to be part of the elite.

How good are Dawkins's analogies? One thing is quite clear. It would not be a good idea to hold a referendum on Einstein's algebra or on the theory of relativity. It is not up to us, obviously, whether or not a factual statement or a mathematical claim is true or false. Similarly, we could have held a vote on whether all Swedes ought to wear face coverings during the COVID-19 pandemic, and while it would have told us something about the beliefs and wishes of us Swedes, it would have told us nothing about whether it was true that masks were an effective way of preventing the spread of infection. As for the pilot and the runway, this is a little trickier since it does not relate to a straightforward factual statement and it therefore makes more sense to have a vote on it. The question is not "Which runway would be safest given the plane's angle of approach?" but "Which runway would you like the pilot to land on?". The response to the latter is likely dependent on the answer to the factual question; most people would want the pilot to do what is safest, but if that is the case, then it depends on the fact that you want this and not simply on safety. It is conceivable that there is an adventurous soul on board the plane who would love to see the pilot make a really dangerous landing.

As I have argued elsewhere, truth—knowledge—is necessary for a well-functioning democracy, but truth is not the only thing that matters, as is inadvertently illustrated by Dawkins's reasoning (Wikforss, 2021, 2023). The question put to the British electorate was not a factual one, such as "Does the EU lead to more research funding for Britain researchers?" or "Would leaving the EU have a negative impact on the economy?" Instead, it was: "Should the United Kingdom remain a member of the European Union or leave the European Union?" This is a question about what you want—not what the world is like. It is perfectly possible to accept all facts in the matter (including facts like the one that British researchers benefit from the EU) and still vote for Brexit. Democratic voting is not about finding out what the reality of the situation is, but about allowing people to exercise their suffrage to influence political decisions.

Is it not irrational to vote for something that you know will have many negative consequences? This is a thorny issue. Firstly, what is negative for one person may be positive for another. In a democracy, people have different interests to preserve and not infrequently these conflict with each other. What is in the interest of a British fisherman (keeping other countries' fishing fleets out of British waters) is somewhat different to what is in the interests of an Oxford don. No doubt, we are quite likely to have many

interests in common. For instance, most people are likely to want a good healthcare system. But in many cases, there are conflicts of interest. It can therefore be entirely rational for a person to vote for Brexit and just as rational for another to vote against it depending on the interests they happen to have. Secondly, we vote not only on the basis of personal interests, but also on the basis of ideas about the general good. If I am convinced that high taxation is good for my country, I can opt to cast my vote for a high tax party even if it does not benefit me personally. We also vote on the basis of ideological considerations. What constitutes an ideology is the subject of much debate, but it is clear that it is about more than just factual beliefs—it relates to overarching values and ideas pertaining to a good society.⁵ Those who are primarily driven by ideological considerations may well vote in a way that goes against their own interests without being the least bit irrational.

It has often been noted that some American voters seem to vote against their own interests, e.g. when someone sick and poor votes against universal health insurance. It is easy to regard voting behaviour of this kind as deeply irrational, but this is not necessarily the case. The person in question may have a very strong aversion to all types of state intervention or perhaps quite simply has no wish for other poor people to be given anything without making an effort. Of course, it may also relate to the fact that they vote on the basis of disinformation—for example, they are deceived into believing that a vote for a certain party may benefit their own finances.⁶ However, even if this type of voter behaviour is not necessarily irrational, it does follow that if people consistently vote against their own interests then free elections will not lead to any improvement in these people's situations. If those who most need universal health insurance vote against all forms of state health insurance, they will not be provided with an improved healthcare situation. A political climate in which voter behaviour is driven by emotions and values that are decoupled from what is in the voters' own interests can thus be problematic. One of the most important functions of democracy is thereby undermined—the opportunity to improve society as a result of people's experiences.

Another complication relates to the issue of whether our *wishes* can be rational or irrational. If I am convinced that leaving the EU brings about nothing but negative consequences for me personally and for society as a

⁵ The Swedish political scientist Herbert Tingsten (1896–1973) devoted himself to examining ideologies such as Nazism, fascism and socialism. According to Tingsten, most ideologies are incorrect precisely because they are based on incorrect factual beliefs.

⁶ Robert Reich discusses this issue in his book *The System. Who Rigged it and How We Fix it* (2020). According to Reich, this is a result of anti-democratic oligarchs gaining an increasing degree of power in the USA and their success in deceiving working class voters into believing it is in their interests to vote conservatively, e.g., through the dissemination of the false message that unemployment is caused by excessive immigration.

whole, is it thus irrational for me to still want the country to leave the EU? Can desires be rational or irrational in the first place? The philosophical debate on this question goes back, at least, to David Hume. In a famous passage in *A Treatise of Human Nature* (1739), he argues that no desire in itself can be said to be sensible or irrational. It does not contradict reason, he claims, to prefer the world's demise rather than being scratched on your finger. Hume thus opposes the idea dating back to antiquity that reason can be used to directly control our wishes and actions. His formulation is concise: "Reason is, and ought only to be, the slave of passions, and can never pretend to any other office than to serve and obey them" (Hume, 1739, 2000 p. 43). For instance, if I want a cold beer, reason can help me achieve that goal, but it cannot influence my wishes directly—that can only be achieved by other wishes. Maybe I really would like a cold beer right now, but my wish to stay sharp and sober ahead of my shift at work today is greater, and I am able to resist the beer. But should it be that the desire for the beer is greater, then it would not in itself be irrational.

It has been much debated how convincing Hume's thesis is. Would it not be entirely against reason to wish for the world's demise? Be that as it may, it is important to note that even if wishes in themselves cannot be rational or irrational, our *actions* can be. What matters then is not theoretical rationality—the rationality of belief—but *practical* rationality, the rationality of action. This depends on two things: what you want (wish) and what you believe. If I want a beer and I believe there is beer in the fridge, it is rational for me to go to the fridge (provided I do not have any other, greater wishes, such as the wish to avoid necking beers at unusual times of day). Given that my political choices are also an action, they can—in the same way—be rational or irrational, and their degree of rationality will always depend both on what I believe and what I want. Even if I think that Swexit (i.e., Sweden's departure from the EU) would be disastrous for Sweden on every conceivable level, it may be rational for me to vote for such an exit—for instance, if I have a very strong desire to give all EU supporters a slap round the face and I accept that it will cost me to do so. Or perhaps I vote entirely based on ideology and consider international cooperation of this overarching kind to always be negative given how it is in tension with national self-governance.

Dawkins is therefore quite right that it would be an incredibly bad idea to hold referenda on factual issues. Even if everyone voted yes to the claim that EU membership results in higher unemployment, it does not follow that this is true. It is a factual issue which is solely resolved by what the world is actually like.⁷ However, it does not follow from this that there

⁷ Under certain circumstances, however, the majority view on a factual issue can constitute evidence for a statement being true. See Wikforss (2025) forthcoming for a discussion.

is anything strange about holding a referendum on EU membership—it is quite alright to ask people whether they want their country to be part of the EU or not.

But is it a good idea to hold referenda on these kinds of complicated political issues? After all, only those with significant factual knowledge are in a position to have a reasonable understanding of what leaving the EU would entail. A problem faced by referenda of all kinds is that they result in a type of rigidity that strikes a discordant note with democracy's great insight into our fallibility and the importance of being able to change course. Dawkins also notes this. "A deceitful politician can be punished at the next election," he writes, but when it comes to Brexit, there will be no next election (Dawkins, 2017). The lure of a referendum for politicians is that they can absolve themselves of responsibility on complicated issues (this was transparently Cameron's objective in the UK), but it comes at the expense of the opportunity to change your mind in light of future knowledge and arguments. This is made worse by the great complexity of the issues. If we assume that Remain is right and that leaving the EU is a disaster for the UK in many different ways (in terms of the economy, research, health, and so on), then the difficulties for voters in getting to grips with the question (even well-educated voters like Dawkins) constitutes a risk. Citizens are voting on a decision that will have very negative consequences without them reasonably being able to know this, and the decision is also binding—it is not possible to easily change course.

Thoughts of this kind lead to an interesting question. Why even let non-experts resolve societal issues that require great expertise? An extension of this reasoning takes us to the idea of a technocracy. If the goal is a better society—improved public health, education, economy, and so on—then why not simply leave it all to the experts? This question has not simply been plucked out of thin air. In a survey conducted by polling company Pew Research in 2017, it emerged that 49 percent of participants around the world believed that technocracy would be better than allowing publicly-elected representatives to make political decisions (Wike, et al., 2017).⁸ Support in Europe was somewhat lower (43 percent), although a huge 68 percent of Hungarian participants preferred a technocracy to democracy (the figure for Sweden was 40 percent). Perhaps most striking is that support for democracy is so weak among young people (18-29 years old), especially in economically developed countries. In the USA, 46 percent of young people indicated that technocracy would be preferable

⁸ At the same time, there is a trend pointing in the opposite direction. The same study notes that direct democracy in which political decisions are made via referenda rather than by publicly elected representatives has great support worldwide. This support is particularly pronounced among populist party voters such as Podemos in Spain (88 percent) and the Sweden Democrats (68 percent). This is in line with the central tenets of populism relating to the idea that democracy is about channelling the "true will of the people."

(as opposed to 36 percent of respondents aged 50 or older). In Sweden, support for technocracy is 13 percent greater among young people than it is among their older counterparts.

The Case for Epistocracy

Democracy is like a hammer. It is a tool with a particular function and if it does not work well then, we should replace it with a better tool. This is how philosopher Jason Brennan reasons on the issue in his book *Against Democracy* (2017). According to Brennan, democracy has no value in itself, but is only of instrumental value, i.e., it is valuable if it helps us to achieve certain goals. Furthermore, he argues that there are good reasons to assume that democracy is a pretty lousy tool, and there are others that would be better. The system advocated by Brennan instead is based on the idea that political power belongs to those who have the required knowledge. A system of this kind is referred to as an *epistocracy*.⁹

The idea behind epistocracy is simple. If certain political decisions are better than others, then it is surely the case that certain citizens are better placed than others to make these decisions—those who have greater competence. Thus, these citizens ought to have more power than others. This idea has its roots in Plato. In *The Republic*, Plato explores the nature of justice and discusses what the ideal state would look like and who ought to govern it. Plato argues against democracy since he considers the risk of citizens being seduced by political rhetoric to be high, and how this in turn may lead to the degeneration of the entire system into tyranny.¹⁰ The expertise rewarded in a democracy, according to Plato, is not what is needed to run a state, but is that needed to win an election. Those leaders who win democratic elections are thus not the most knowledgeable, but merely those best able to manipulate the people. Plato describes the democratic leader as one who makes use of false and boastful words, who rejects moderation, praises laziness as a sign of being of “good descent” and criticises caution as being unmanly. The democratic leader eventually becomes nothing more than a demagogic tyrant surrounded by yes-men who stroke his ego. In an article from 2018, the American journalist Olivia Goldhill poses the question as to whether these qualities are at all reminiscent of a certain American president (Goldhill, 2018).¹¹

⁹ The term was first used by Estlund (2003).

¹⁰ One should, of course, keep in mind that Plato meant something different by the words “state” and “democracy” to what we do. A state was not a nation in the modern sense but a Greek city-state, an area comprised solely of a city (Athens or Sparta) and its immediate surroundings. And while Greek democracy was a form of popular government, only a minority in the city benefitted from suffrage: free men (ergo, no women or slaves). There were also no freedoms or rights—even free men could be banished for their views.

¹¹ The re-election of Trump in 2024, despite his attempt to overrule the election results of 2020, and the resulting dismantling of the democratic system of checks and balances in the United States make Plato’s point even more pertinent.

Who, then, is competent to govern? Plato, of course, thought the state ought to be governed by philosophers, since they were among the very wisest. The philosopher's education, according to Plato, means that they are in close contact with ideas and can thus make decisions in accordance with what is ideal—for example, in accordance with what justice actually is. They are also particularly well-suited since they have been trained to control their desires. The ideal state is authoritarian and governed by a philosophical king. However, there are less authoritarian forms of epistocracy too. One idea is simply to allow the well-educated to have more votes than others. This idea is found in the writings of John Stuart Mill. This may seem a tad surprising given that Mill's ideas form the basis for contemporary liberal democracy, but we ought to remember that this democracy was originally intended to apply to a select group—that of enlightened men. In his defense, Mill also considered a good education for all to be a central tenet of the democratic system.

Jason Brennan sees further possible forms of epistocracy. For example, one could limit voting rights to constituents who pass a qualification exam or hold a suffrage lottery in which a group of competent citizens are drawn at random before receiving full training in politically-relevant knowledge (Brennan, 2017, pp. 278-290). All these iterations would be, in his view, better than a democracy containing ignorant and irrational voters. He admits that systems of this kind have never truly been tested and that of the systems that have been tried, democracy is the best. However, he argues, this does not mean that democracy is the best possible system: there may be another, even better one that we have never tried. Brennan's central thesis is precisely this: if there is a better working alternative, we ought to use it. In his book, he seeks to argue that an epistocracy would—in many ways—work better than those democracies we have at present.

Brennan uses various kinds of arguments to reach this startling conclusion. One is simply that we become worse people through political participation. In this regard, Brennan questions a core idea in democratic theory, found already in Mill: that political participation is, in various ways, good for our character. It makes us autonomous, independent thinkers, it trains us to be more rational (since our decisions actually matter in a democracy), and it makes us moral and more empathetic. As far as Brennan is concerned, this notion is altogether false. Political participation makes us angry and rabid, engaging us in tribalism and other types of skewed thinking. Is he right in this regard? The question is empirical and not entirely easy to answer. Political developments in recent years indicate that he has a point, even if it is hard to know what kind of people we would have been without politics. We were hardly pleasant before the emergence of modern democracy, e.g., in the 16th century, when witch burnings and other public executions were popular events. On the contrary,

empirical evidence shows how recent centuries have made us better people and how there has been moral development. For instance, although our present day is characterised by great disagreement on values, there is hardly anyone arguing that slavery would be a good idea. It is reasonable to believe that this development is intimately tied precisely to modern democracy and its notion that all people are of equal value and have certain fundamental rights. Despite the fact that political participation can make us most unpleasant in everyday life, it has still led to the moral development of our societies.

Brennan's central argument, however, is epistemological. He refers to research, showing that voters are hopelessly ignorant when it comes to political issues. This incompetence, according to him, is a good reason not to let them exercise political power over others—the consequences of them doing so are quite simply too negative. It is necessary to minimise the power of ignorant voters in order to protect innocent people. His point is not that those citizens with greater knowledge ought to automatically have greater political authority, but rather that those who lack knowledge should not be permitted to exercise power over others. "The epistocrat does not have to argue in favour of all experts being bosses," he writes (Brennan, 2017, p. 46). It is enough to assert that incompetent and foolish people should not be permitted to be the boss of anyone else:

If we, the electorate, are bad at politics, if we succumb to fantasies and delusions, or disregard the facts, then people die. We fight unnecessary wars. We implement poor political measures that perpetuate poverty. We over-regulate pharmaceuticals or under-regulate carbon emissions.

This argument is well worth examining in further detail given that it casts light in an interesting fashion on the issue of the role of knowledge in a democracy.

Let us begin with the empirical statement that we, as voters, are ignorant. Unfortunately, there is plenty of evidence to substantiate this. Brennan begins by pointing out how ignorant the British public was about facts that were relevant to the 2016 referendum. Leave voters believed that EU migrants constituted 20 percent of the UK population, while Remain voters believed that figure to be 10 percent. In reality, the true figure was 5 percent. Voters from both groups overestimated the total sum of child benefit payments made by the UK to other countries (by a factor of 40 to 100), massively underestimated the extent of foreign investments from the EU and overestimated the corresponding figure from China (Brennan, 2017, p. 2).

Extensive research in political science finds the same thing. Brennan refers to research looking back at 1940s America that began to catalogue

what ordinary citizens knew about politics. Political scientists have found the results are very disappointing. Brennan lists some examples: during an election year, most people are unable to name any congressional candidates in their district; most people do not know which party is in power in Congress; they overestimate how much money is spent on aid and on social welfare payments; and they are unaware of the fact that crime has fallen (Brennan, 2017, pp. 48-49). This type of ignorance constitutes a threat toward the key functions of democracy: to give a mandate and to hold elected officials accountable for their policies. Voters also have lousy knowledge of historical events. One rather hair-raising fact is that 40 percent of all Americans are unaware of who the USA fought during the Second World War, while 73 per cent are unaware what the Cold War was about. When key historical knowledge disappears from the public consciousness, it is difficult to learn from past mistakes.

It is, however, worth noting that there are national differences in this regard. American voters in particular stand out as being especially ignorant.¹² Research shows that European voters tend to do better when it comes to political knowledge. Among the things measured are political expertise, such as unemployment rates, whether the budgetary deficit is increasing, or how many refugees Sweden accepted during a defined period; knowledge of the political system, including how many members of parliament there are, or which parties are in government; and knowledge of political candidates and party representatives. The political scientist Henrik Oscarsson notes that while it is notoriously difficult to compare countries, voters in northern European multi-party systems are among the more well-informed (Oscarsson, 2006a; Oscarsson 2006n; Oscarsson 2017).

However, those who believe in epistocracy are not satisfied with pointing out that voters are often extremely ignorant in terms of basic political knowledge. They also highlight that even if voters were knowledgeable on these matters, this would still be insufficient to enable them to responsibly participate in politics. Responsible participation requires far more detailed knowledge of party manifestos and candidates' political experience, as well as knowledge that allows voters to determine which policy proposals would best fulfil the goals she has as a voter. Maybe I want to see a strong economy and reduced crime—in order to know which measures would best serve these goals, I need expert knowledge in economics and criminology. Is protectionism good for the economy? Do harsher punishments lead to reductions in crime? Epistocrats are also keen to point out how emotionally driven and irrational we are, especially when it comes to pol-

¹² See Achen & Bartels (2017) for a detailed discussion of the situation in the USA, and of what conclusions should be drawn from this.

itics. Tribalism means we engage in motivated thinking—so-called knowledge resistance—where we reject available knowledge that does not align with our political or cultural group.¹³ We deploy skewed arguments to protect factual beliefs that have become central to our own political identities, whether these relate to crime, the economy, the environment, or immigration. We thereby avoid acquiring important knowledge that is actually available, and the result is poor political decisions.

The Epistemic Case for Democracy

Jason Brennan's reasoning is directly contrary to the so-called *epistemic argument* in favour of democracy. This is based on the idea that in a democracy, there is a greater likelihood of making good political decisions than in systems where only a few rule. One reason for this is thought to be that even if we as individuals are rather hopeless, we are very competent as a collective electorate. In her book *Democratic Reason* (2013), philosopher Hélène Landemore develops this argument in detail. According to Landemore, the main reason to use the decision-making procedures of democracy is that it is a *reliable* procedure—it tends to lead to good decisions. Of course, democracies do sometimes make poor decisions, but according to Landemore, decisions in non-democracies are generally much worse. The biggest and most disastrous mistakes in world history cannot be attributed to democracies.

Those who defend the epistemic argument usually refer to various mathematical theorems, including Condorcet's jury theorem. This is based on the idea that a majority decision leads to the truth – provided certain conditions are fulfilled.¹⁴ A jury process is envisaged in which the jurors' task is to determine facts, such as whether a certain person has actually shot another person (determining what the law says when facts are established is, however, up to the court). Provided the jurors are all motivated and have some ability to reach the truth (better than chance), and provided they are independent of each other (i.e., they vote in accordance with what they themselves believe), then the probability is greater that the group will reach the truth than the probability of each juror doing so individually. If the group is sufficiently large, for instance if it includes all citizens, then the probability that the majority is correct increases and begins to verge on absolute certainty. Another well-known theorem is the miracle of aggregation theorem, which is based on the idea that if the errors of a large democracy are randomly distributed, then it will work well

¹³ For a philosophical clarification and discussion of the nature of knowledge resistance, see Glüer & Wikforss (2022).

¹⁴ For a detailed defence, see Goodin & Spiekermann (2018).

from a knowledge perspective—even if the majority of voters are ignorant. Ignorant voters will simply balance each other out, precisely because the errors are random.

Brennan's objection to arguments making use of these and similar theorems is that they are based on false assumptions (Brennan, 2017, pp. 233–260). For instance, voters are not independent of each other but engage in tribal thinking; that is, their beliefs and preferences are largely dependent on their group affiliations rather than on evidence and good arguments. To make things worse, Brennan argues, it is false that individual citizens perform better than chance, which is a prerequisite for Condorcet's theorem to work.¹⁵ Errors committed are not entirely random but are systematic. Different types of psychological biases and skewed thinking mean that we end up doing things wrong systematically. For example, confirmation bias means we tend to seek out arguments that confirm our own beliefs and avoid those that contradict them. The Dunning–Kruger effect means that the less you know about something, the worse you are at assessing how competent you and others are. This leads to systematic errors when evaluating how competent a politician is—the more ignorant you are, the more competent you believe the politician to be. In the best of all worlds, the assumptions these theorems are founded upon would be true, and in the best of all worlds, this would mean that democracy led to good decisions. But that is not the world we live in.

Brennan's argumentation is a tad skewed at this point. A *conceivable, ideal* form of governance (epistocracy) is measured against actual, far-from-ideal versions of another (democracy).¹⁶ No epistocracy has ever existed, and it is easy to imagine the problems that one would entail in practice—great power without accountability rarely brings about anything good. Hélène Landemore chooses instead to compare democracy with other, actually extant systems and concludes in this regard that democratic decision-making processes work best. We do not live in the best of all worlds, which means that democratic decisions are not always the right ones, but we live in a world where political decisions that are made democratically tend to be better than those made by other means. Landemore also stresses how the procedures of democracy presuppose that the institutions of a liberal democracy are in place: freedom of expression, independent media, education, and so on. She particularly emphasises the fact that epistemic diversity is crucial and refers to John Stuart Mill's

¹⁵ Hans Rosling seems to agree with him in his book *Factfulness: Ten Reasons We're Wrong About the World* (2018). One of Rosling's points is that when it comes to many factual issues of political relevance, we are no better than a chimpanzee at getting the right answer, i.e. no better than chance. Rosling describes the book as "the last battle in my lifelong mission to fight devastating global ignorance. It is my last attempt to make an impact on the world: to change people's ways of thinking."

¹⁶ This contorted argumentation is highlighted by Ludvig Beckman (2017) in his review of Brennan's book.

idea that we must create a “marketplace of ideas” where different positions encounter each other in order for the truth to emerge. Landmore argues that majority decisions made without this liberal background can be downright harmful:

Illiberal or authoritarian democracies that foster conformism of views and stifle dissent risk turning both deliberation and majority rule into dangerous mechanisms for collective unreason. (Landmore, 2013, p. 234)

Landmore’s book was published in 2013, a few years prior to the major political events of 2016, and it is thus not clear what she would say about the so-called post-truth era. However, some claim that what characterizes our time is precisely how the conditions required to deliver good decision-making in a democracy are not currently being fulfilled. In *An Epistemic Theory of Democracy* (2019), Robert Goodin and Kai Spiekermann examine the societal circumstances that lead to the decision-making processes of democracy resulting in good political decisions. They conclude by discussing the present day and argue that the election of Trump and the Brexit referendum in the UK represent examples of situations in which the epistemic value of democracy has been undermined (Goodin & Spiekermann, 2019).¹⁷ Both votes were characterised by being based on outright lies and the systematic manipulation of voters. From this perspective, it is possible to characterise our time—the post-truth era—as precisely such a situation in which circumstances make it unlikely that the majority will make correct decisions. The widespread dissemination of disinformation minimizes the likelihood that voters are right, affective polarisation and emotionally charged rhetoric increase the risk that voters are engaging in tribal thinking, and an infected debate makes it less likely that we are able to reach the truth on key societal issues by means of collective strength. The damage caused by the post-truth era is thus very clear to see. It is not only that the power of voters is weakened when they are governed by disinformation and propaganda—it is also the case that the political decisions deteriorate in quality too.

Things are, however, complex and this relates to the fact I mentioned previously political decisions depend not only on what we believe about the world, but also on what we want. Both those who defend the epistemic argument in favour of democracy and those who defend epistocracy therefore make an assumption that can be questioned: the idea that

¹⁷ Presumably, they would agree that this holds for the 2024 U.S. presidential election as well, where Donald Trump systematically spread disinformation, for instance about immigrants. In addition, of course, the fact that he emerged as the candidate of the Republican Party in 2024 could only be understood against the background of an effort to rewrite the history of the January 6th storming of the U.S. Capitol, describing it not as a violent attempt to prevent the peaceful transfer of power but as “a day of love.”

there are *correct* answers to political questions.¹⁸ Brennan is very explicit about this and states that his argument rests on three basic principles, of which the assumption of truth is the first. However, what makes political issues complex is how they not only encompass factual issues but also questions about values or preferences. The question therefore also arises as to whether there are correct answers when it comes to values—whether *moral knowledge* can even be acquired.

Brennan is conscious of this problem and observes that the arguments in favour of an epistocracy presuppose not only that there is scientific expertise, but also that there is moral expertise—people who know better when it comes to contemplating how society should be shaped. He proposes that certain preferences are more enlightened than others and notes that there is an interesting correlation between these preferences and knowledge. As people become more well-informed, they want to see a lower degree of economic regulation, they are more positive about free trade and less positive about protectionism, they do not believe in harsh punishments, and they become more positive about free abortions and affirmative action (Brennan, 2017, p. 59).

Now, this reasoning is obviously not enough to demonstrate there are moral truths and moral experts. It is quite possible that the connection between political preferences and knowledge is based precisely on greater knowledge of factual issues (you know, for instance, that when abortion rights are curtailed, there is no reduction in the number of abortions—they merely take place in more dangerous conditions). Landemore focuses on this and suggests precisely that political disagreement can often be traced to disagreement on factual issues (Landemore, 2013, pp. 214–215). She also believes that as long as we accept that factual statements are true or false, this is enough to support the idea that some political decisions are better than others—those based on correct assumptions about facts.

The question is whether we can go further. Is it possible to argue that some political decisions are better than others in the sense that they are *morally* better? Landemore argues that this is the case. She distinguishes between two types of value judgments: fact-sensitive principles and fundamental values.¹⁹ An example of the former is the statement that if Iran's nuclear energy programme constitutes a threat to global peace, then the USA should do what it can to prevent Iran from acquiring nuclear capabilities. Another example of a fact-sensitive principle is the statement that if an increase in the minimum wage causes greater unemployment, we should not increase the minimum wage. These types of principles depend on the assumption that certain facts apply (*if* something is the

¹⁸ For a critique of this assumption, see Weale (2018, pp. 89–90).

¹⁹ The distinction comes from Cohen (2003, pp. 211–245).

case, *then...*), but they also depend on certain value assumptions—in this case that peace is important, and unemployment is bad. Landemore goes on to suggest that these value assumptions can, in turn, lead on to more fundamental value judgments that are not dependent on empirical facts, e.g., the principle that all other things being equal, human life should be protected. The question of whether political decisions can be said to be correct (in a stronger sense than based on correct factual beliefs), thus becomes a question of whether these fundamental moral principles can be true.

The question of moral truth is the subject of an extensive debate within meta ethics that I shall have to set aside here. What should be noted, however, is that even if one accepts that moral knowledge exists (and I am inclined to do so), it is clear that it is a kind of knowledge that cannot be obtained in the way that we acquire ordinary factual knowledge. There is no empirical evidence to refer to and no experiments that can resolve the matter. We must instead rely on our intuitive judgments of different situations (e.g., a situation in which a child is about to drown) and our ability to think rationally in order to try and find well-founded moral judgments.²⁰ One such judgment is that human suffering is something bad in itself and that human well-being is something good. Political decisions that lead to great human suffering are therefore bad—incorrect.

It is also important to note that even if you believe in certain fundamental principles of this kind, it is consistent with a form of value pluralism on a more “superficial” level. For instance, it is reasonable—given that we humans are inherently different—to assume that what makes us unhappy and happy may vary. One person may value a life of freedom far from traditional family life and quotidian routines. Another person may value the opposite: an orderly life in a nuclear family. This means holding different values on one level; but these people may still be entirely in agreement with each other about the fundamental principles that human suffering is bad and human well-being is good. In the same way, it may be that certain communities value a certain form of traditional morality, while others value a different one, without this meaning there is any difference between them when it comes to the most fundamental of values. The important thing from this perspective is that society, to the greatest possible extent, accommodates this variation in terms of “superficial” values—such as, which type of family model we value—while at the same time ensuring that fundamental values are upheld. In other words, the important thing is to accommodate a form of value pluralism within the framework of democracy’s fundamental values, such as the idea that all human beings are

²⁰ See Rawls (1971) and his defense of the idea of a reflective equilibrium, which is precisely about using critical thinking to find a form of balance between moral intuitions about individual cases and general principles.

of equal value.

Landemore argues for a similar position (Landemore 2013, p. 219). She accepts the idea that there is a set of fundamental, universal values, but also that there are local, cultural differences when it comes to conventional values. She asserts that democratic decisions are better both in the local sense—they tend to correlate with the values people have in a given society—and in the universal sense—they tend to respect universal values. It could be added, as I have already indicated, that the two are connected. Precisely because democracy accepts some local variation (value pluralism), it is better in a universal sense (when it comes to people's suffering and well-being).

Even if you believe in objective values, however, there are reasons to be doubtful about Brennan's idea that it is possible to designate certain people as moral experts. This is tied to the fact noted above that there is no form of generally accepted method to determine what is morally right and wrong. In this regard, value disagreement differs from factual disagreement. Admittedly, Brennan acknowledges that the issue of who knows more than others would doubtless be contentious.²¹ However, he emphasizes that the fact something is controversial does not inherently mean that there is no truth to something, nor that we do not know what truth looks like. People dispute all sorts of things, even in areas such as evolutionary biology or microeconomics, where some people know the truth. But Brennan makes it easy for himself in this regard. It is not difficult to determine who is a scientific expert. For example, we can fall back on institutional criteria. In order to be an expert in evolutionary biology, you need a thorough education in the subject, you need a Ph.D., and you need to be embedded in a scientific context where your own research is assessed by other researchers via a number of means.²² But what does a moral expert look like? What training does such an individual have, and which control mechanisms exist to determine whether that person has made a mistake? Of course, Plato envisaged that a good philosophical education would be enough, but it is unlikely that many would accept that line of reasoning today. Martin Heidegger (1889–1976) was a well-educated philosopher, especially in Greek philosophy, but he was also a Nazi.²³

Balancing between Epistocracy and Populism

The difference between facts and values and between means and ends,

²¹ This problem is one of David Estlund's main objections to epistocracy (Estlund, 2003). For a discussion, see also Dahl (1989, Chapter 4).

²² I discuss this in Wikforss (2025), forthcoming.

²³ On Heidegger and Nazism, see Olterman (2014).

demonstrates the great weakness of epistocracy as a political system. Political decisions are not just about facts but are also about values—about our goals—and these should be determined by us, the citizens, rather than by self-appointed “moral experts.”²⁴ Brennan is right that present-day societies are infinitely complex and that it often requires great expert knowledge in order to achieve the goals set by elected representatives—whether these relate to crime, climate change, or unemployment. In a representative democracy, this is resolved through a political system where political decisions are made by elected representatives in consultation with subject specific experts, e.g., in various authorities and bodies. The power held by these experts is always delegated to them by the elected representatives. It also relates to the fact that these elected representatives possess *political* expertise. They know how the system works, they have an overarching vision for society, and they can drive through various political changes. But, again, there is cause to be highly sceptical of Brennan’s assertion that we also ought to hand over the issue of our *goals* to the experts.

Populism and epistocracy can thus be described as two extremes when it comes to the role of experts in a democracy. Populists want a politics that is the direct expression of the will of the people. For instance, they want more referenda to limit the influence of expert knowledge on political decisions. Epistocrats hold that experts should make decisions about both the ends and the means. Representative democracy avoids both extremes and allows the political ends to be determined by its citizens while also accommodating expert knowledge as the basis of decisions. The experts must then evaluate the means but not the ends. This involves compromises that are not always successful, and there is a constant risk that representative democracy slips too far in one direction or the other. One risk (the one Plato was concerned by) is that a populist demagogue seduces his citizens and implements policy that goes against all expert knowledge, making society dysfunctional. Another risk is that democracy borders on technocracy in which ordinary people have little opportunity in reality to influence political decisions. Many have argued that the way in which laws are enacted in the EU (and then become part of national legislation) constitutes an example of the rise of technocracy. Representative democracy must always strike a balance between these risks.²⁵ However, when the balancing act succeeds, it manages to combine popular influence and expert knowledge in a way that no other system achieves.

²⁴ See Christiano (2008) for a discussion. According to Christiano, the task of citizens is to define which goals society should strive for, while the duty of legislators is to prepare the means to achieve those ends. Brennan (2017) criticizes this idea (pp. 279–281).

²⁵ This is a central pillar of thought in Rosenfeld (2019).

In fact, Brennan notes that democratic societies function better than one would expect given how ignorant and irrational their voters are (Brennan, 2017, p. 235).²⁶ At present, it is best to live in liberal democracies, he writes, rather than in dictatorships, one-party states, oligarchies, and absolute monarchies (p. 261). The explanation, according to Brennan, is that there are different types of epistocratic controls in a democratic system, including expert authorities who provide the necessary scientific expertise, as well as experienced politicians who know how to implement those promised policies. He also points to political science research showing a series of mediating factors between what a majority currently wants and the laws enacted and decisions made: interested citizens can debate and apply pressure to politicians; major state bureaucracies (such as the army) live a life of their own; politicians are significantly better informed than voters; and political parties have the power to make decisions independently of voters' views (p. 267). These mediating factors are associated with representative democracy. Citizens have less direct influence in such a democracy compared with a system reliant on greater elements of direct democracy, but the advantage is precisely how political decisions involve expert knowledge of various kinds. And the great advantage of democracy also remains: when things go wrong, i.e., when voters are dissatisfied with the results, it is possible to vote those in power out of office. This ability is not afforded to citizens of autocracies or epistocracies.

Of course, there are many other objections to epistocracies, e.g., objections related to how democracies feature fairer processes. Those who deploy the epistemic argument in favour of democracy, such as Landemore, accept Brennan's assumption that democracy is merely a tool and its value is purely instrumental. However, it is possible to reject this idea. Perhaps democracy is in fact more like poetry or art? Perhaps equal suffrage holds a symbolic value as a sign of the equal value of all humans?²⁷ However, even if we agree with Brennan's instrumentalism, his arguments in favour of epistocracy and against democracy are not convincing. Epistocracy would be a worse tool than democracy given that political decisions are about more than just factual knowledge. You could even provide an instrumental argument in favour of the idea that society ought to be based on the assumption that all people are of equal value (just as you could set out an instrumental argument in favour of art). A society of this kind would be a better society than all the versions where this assumption is not made—it simply makes us better people. Universal suffrage serves

²⁶ See also p. 25.

²⁷ Brennan (2017) discusses this idea in Chapter 5, *Politics Is Not A Poem*. For a critique of Brennan on this point, see Beckman (2017). As Beckman emphasizes, it is not an either-or issue—you can recognize both that democracy has a value in itself and that it is of great instrumental value.

not only to distribute political power but also to remind us of the equal value of all people.

Ironically enough, there is also a risk that an epistocracy may lose one of the knowledge-related advantages offered by democracy. As I have argued elsewhere, democracy is based on the idea that people's experiential knowledge is given the opportunity to influence politics—experiences of poverty and oppression, for instance. In an epistocracy, the knowledgeable hold power, but there is a clear risk these knowledgeable people originate from a fairly narrow demographic background so the experiential knowledge they bring with them is thereby overly limited.²⁸ Brennan is aware of this problem and notes that political knowledge is not evenly distributed among all demographic groups. White people know more than black people, people in the northeast of the USA know more than people in the south, and high-income earners know more than the poor (Brennan, 2017, p. 301). However, he also argues that in a democracy, governments serve certain interests more than others. Additionally, this objection presupposes that disadvantaged citizens who receive less power in an epistocracy know how to vote in order to advance their own interests, and that is not true. Experts would know better how their situation should be improved.

This may be the case—if the experts of an epistocracy are assumed to be omniscient, rational altruists. Yet it goes without saying that such experts do not exist in reality (which Brennan acknowledges) and there is a big risk that those who have not experienced vulnerability of various degrees lack the knowledge (and will) required to improve others' living conditions. Thus, these groups must have a voice in society, and that requires a (well-functioning) democracy. For example, it is difficult for a white American to understand what it is like to be black and to regard the police as a potentially lethal threat. Brennan's central argument can in this regard be used against him. We must be protected from governance by the ignorant, and in this case, this pertains to those who are ignorant of people's experiences and suffering.

As for political ignorance, there is also a better solution than the abolition of democracy: counteracting ignorance. This requires many different interventions. Schools should provide pupils with the knowledge required for them to make well-founded political choices and to compensate for knowledge-related injustices caused by inequalities in social background.²⁹ An active, lifelong education system should make it possible for large groups in society to continuously update their knowledge.

²⁸ See Estlund (2003), for a version of the demographic objection.

²⁹ In *Alternative Facts*, I argue that the dominating pedagogical theory in much of the Western world during the last few decades, so called constructivism, has failed its pupils in terms of this key democratic mission.

A well-functioning library system should reach the citizens. Researchers should disseminate relevant knowledge through different types of popular scientific initiatives, and high-quality journalism should help citizens to obtain knowledge about the present day, gain insight into politicians' activities, and cast light on the consequences of political decisions. And, naturally, public debates must be reliable and well-functioning, offering space for different points of view and assessment of arguments. The institutions of modern democracy are all key to counteracting the ignorance of its citizens. No doubt, in the new high-choice information environment, there are powerful forces in the opposite direction, exploiting the freedom of speech in order to prevent available knowledge from reaching the public: varieties of disinformation and active science denialism. However, again, the solution is not dismantling democracy, but to boost its immune system, so that it can defend itself against the enemies of knowledge.

It is also important to strengthen political engagement in various ways. One exciting contemporary field of research in democracy theory relates to how representative democracy can be renewed, and how by means of different types of civic participation it is possible to increase political involvement, and thus, political knowledge. This can involve citizens participating in budget discussions at a local level, which has been trialled in Scotland, or the organisation of various types of civic groups which prepare proposals for various forms of societal change.³⁰ When the Republic of Ireland surprisingly voted to legalise abortion in 2018, the initiative had been put to a vote precisely as the result of such a citizens' assembly. One hope is that this type of civic participation will not only lead to increased engagement and knowledge but also help to counteract anti-democratic forces (McKerrell, 2019).

In the face of rapidly accelerating global democratic decline, it is essential that we are able to articulate the strengths of democracy as a system. Actual democracies are always flawed in some ways—for example, there is the constant danger of democracy handing too much power over to the experts, or to lobbying groups using their financial strength to exert pressure on power, and there is always the worry that public participation is waning. These should be examined and discussed, and we should think of ways to improve and innovate democracy. At the same time, however, we need to not lose sight of what we know about existing political systems. Empirical evidence shows that democracies always outperform autocracies when it comes to creating basic things that most humans value, such as health and equality, and avoiding humanitarian disasters, such as wars and famines (V-Dem Institute, 2022). And while the idea of an epistocracy should be taken seriously philosophically, in particular since it

³⁰ For an overview, see Smith (2009).

highlights the essential role of knowledge in a well-functioning society, it remains a philosophical thought experiment that we should be very hesitant to implement in the real world.

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